

CHARACTERISTICS OF COMPRESSION STRATEGY IN SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION

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Abstract: The given publication work is aimed at revealing the fact that simultaneous interpretation is being an initial one day by day. In the process of synchronous interpretation there several strategies to help interpreters, being one of them compression strategy is the main key point of our article.

Today the role of foreign languages is getting more and more crucial in every sphere of human life and of course English language is being № 1 foreign language around the world. Every international conferences, meetings, delegations are held on English, due to this fact the role of interpretation is also ultimately. The researchers' interest to simultaneous interpretation started growing approximately in 60's of XX century. Studies in simultaneous interpretation were conducted in parallel with psycholinguistic studies, because the simultaneous interpretation attracted attention of linguists as well as psycholinguists. The special attention was pinned at the method of compression which goes together with simultaneous interpretation. There are many scholars who investigated this sphere. Among whom G.V.Chernov, I.A.Zimnyaya, A.F.Shiryayev, A.D.Schweizer, V.A.Artemov, I.V.Gurin have a remarkable place. Ilyuhin defined the concept of strategy in simultaneous interpretation as «the means of fulfilling translation task» [1, 203] and divided it into two: simultaneous interpretation strategies connected to the factor of time and simultaneous interpretation strategies conditioned by permanent factors. He included the strategy of compression which is the object of our research into the group of simultaneous interpretation strategies conditioned by permanent factors.

The task of a translator covers not only conveying the exact meaning of a source text, but also conveying it fully. However, conditions of simultaneous interpretation do not give an interpreter a liberty to convey the source text completely as in written translation. For example, in cases when the speed of an orator 'speech is fast, the interpreter is consciously compelled to reduce the size

of a source text. A.F.Shiryayev says several factors cause the text reduction process.¹

- Firstly, when performing translation from one language into another the text size increases. For instance, the number of syllables increases as much as one and half times when the written translation is performed from English into Russian with all the possible editing, but in oral interpretation where editing is not possible as in written translation the syllables number increases as much as two times. Therefore, if the speed of an orator's speech is high or medium, it is impossible to get translation without reducing the text size.
- Secondly, in order for the interpreter to follow the source text successfully he/she must make very short pauses while interpretation. Otherwise the interpreter might miss a very important piece of information. Therefore, without making short pauses while translation the interpreter risks to miss some significant portion of a source text.
- Third, in cases when speed of the orator's speech is high the interpreter may make mistakes without proper performance of linguistic mechanisms in the process of switching from translation language to the source language. That is why conditions under which the simultaneous interpretation takes place, especially when orators 'speed is high or medium compel an interpreter to use linguistic transformation to the message in order to reduce the source text size. The interpreter utilizes the compression mechanism for successful and effective fulfilment of text reduction. The method of reducing syllables number without damage to the communicative task put forth by an interpreter is referred to as compression. Compression is process of compressing by preserving information which is essential for the present communicative tasks and putting aside the remaining part.

Compression strategy is likely to happen when repeating and odd information can be found in source text. According to A.D.Schweizer compression of information can be reached by omitting excessive information in a statement. The excessive information mentioned here according to him is elements complimented in the context of situation and communication. As for fulfilling communication task, unimportant pieces of information which bear no argumentative value are exposed to compression, that is words meant for making a statement more colourful, more pleasant, synonymic streak of words,

¹ Ширяев А. Ф. Синхронный перевод: Деятельность синхронного переводчика и методика преподавания синхронного перевода / А. Ф. Ширяев. – М.: Воениздат, 1979. – 183 с

introductory words, sometimes (when time is too short) kind remarks, irrelevant to the topic words are dropped.

It is a well known fact that difference in languages structures imposes on interpreters additional hardships while translation. In three languages out of ten mostly used languages (English, German, Arabic, Russian, Chinese, French, Italian, Japan, Portugal, Spanish) by simultaneous interpreters have syntactic system in which verb's position is at the end of a sentence. As for Arabic, its verb on the contrary is mostly at the beginning of a sentence. This fact creates challenges when translating into Kazakh, because the verb comes at the end of a sentence in Kazakh. Therefore natural peculiarities in the lexical, syntactic systems of languages lie in the basis of translation transformation.² Barkhudarov defined translation process as "interlingua transforming or reforming a text in one language into another". In accordance with this viewpoint compression mechanism can also be defined as reforming or transforming a text in one language into another reducing number of syllables. It means using wide-range methods and approaches of lexical-semantic and grammatical transformation enables compression to be performed more effectively. Thus, the fact that using the strategy of compression is conditioned by topical situation and linguistic excess assures a speaker conveys his communicative intentions briefly and exactly and provides stylistically appropriate formation of a translation text.

By the help of abovementioned info we can surely say that the characteristics of compression strategy is of course ups on lexical-semantic feature of target language, however this strategy is one of the most used strategy by interpreters.

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